

**O`ZBEK XALQI TURMUSHI BILAN BOG`LIQ KASB-KOR TURLARI
(Temirchilik kasb-hunari doirasida)**

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Annotatsiya. IX – X asrlarda Movarounnahr va Xorazm aholisining asosiy qismi sug`orma dehqonchilik bilan shug`ullanar edi. Sug`orish tarmoqlari vositasida sug`orilib obod etilgan serunum vohalarda g`allakorlik, sholikorlik, paxtachilik, sabzavotchilik, polizchilik va bog`dorchilik yuqori darajada rivoj topgan edi. Voha hududlarida paxtachilik katta o`rinni egallagan. Qolaversa, bog`dorchilik madaniyati yuksak darajada rivojlangan. Xalqimizda qadimdan sabzavot va poliz ekinlari ham serob bo`lib, qovunlari nihoyatda shirali bo`lgan.

Kalit so`zlar: maqol, temirchilik, tegirmon, to`qimachilik, kulolchilik, chilangarlik, miskarlik, zargarlik, shishasozlik va duradgorlik.

**TYPES OF OCCUPATIONS RELATED TO THE LIFE OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE
(within the profession of blacksmithing)**

Abstract. In the 9th - 10th centuries, the majority of the inhabitants of Movarounnahr and Khorezm were engaged in irrigated agriculture. In serunum oases, which were irrigated by means of irrigation networks, grain growing, rice growing, cotton growing, vegetable growing, policing and horticulture developed at a high level. In the oases, cotton cultivation occupies a large place. Besides, horticultural culture is highly developed. Vegetables and fruit crops have been abundant in our nation since ancient times, and melons are extremely juicy.

Key words: proverb, blacksmithing, mill, textile, pottery, blacksmithing, coppersmithing, jewelry, glassmaking and carpentry.

**ВИДЫ ЗАНЯТИЙ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ЖИЗНЬЮ УЗБЕКСКОГО НАРОДА
(в рамках профессии кузнечного дела)**

Аннотация. В IX-X веках большая часть жителей Моваруннахра и Хорезма занималась орошаемым земледелием. В серунных оазисах, орошавшихся с помощью ирригационных сетей, на высоком уровне развивалось зерноводство, рисоводство, хлопководство, овощеводство, полицейское дело и садоводство. В оазисах большое место занимает выращивание хлопка. Кроме того, высоко развита садоводческая культура. Овощи и плодовые культуры в нашем народе издревле были в изобилии, а дыни чрезвычайно сочны.

Ключевые слова: пословица, кузнечное дело, мельница, текстильное дело, гончарное дело, кузнечное дело, медное дело, ювелирное дело, стекольное и столярное дело.

Kasb – kishining mehnat faoliyati, doimiy mashg`uloti turi, muayyan ish turini beradigan bilim, mahorat, tajribani talab etadi. Kasblar, odatda, shaxsning asosiy tirikchilik manbai hisoblanadi. Xalq xo`jaligining turlicha ishlab chiqarish tarmoqlarida xalqimizning asrlar bo`yi

qilib kelgan ijodiy mehnati jarayonida yaratilgan va yaratilayotgan bir qancha kasb-hunar turlari mavjud. Jumladan:

Qadimdan chorvachilikka alohida e'tibor berilgan. Mamlakatning dasht va tog'oldi yaylovlarida qo'y va echkilar, yilqilar va tuyalar boqilgan. Qishloqlarda qoramollar behisob bo'lgan. Chorvachilik mamlakat aholisini ta'minlabgina qolmasdan, xo'jalikning hamma sohalari uchun ot-ulovlar ham yetkazib bergan¹.

Qadimdan yurtimiz shaharlarida to'qimachilik, kulolchilik, chilangarlik, miskarlik, zargarlik, shishasozlik va duradgorlik kabi kasb-hunarlar rivoj topgan. Ushbu holat esa, shubhasiz, shaharning qiyofasini tubdan o'zgartirgan. Savdo-sotiq jonlangan, boshqa mamlakatlar bilan aloqalar yo'lga qo'yilgan. Turli xil hunarmandchilik tarmoqlarining rivojlanishi natijasida katta-katta gumbazli toq-u ravoqli va peshtoqli imoratlar, ustaxonalar, masjid, madrasa, maqbara, xonaqoh va karvonsaroylar qad ko'targan. Shaharlar esa o'nlab hunarmandchilik markaziga aylanib borgan. Bundan tashqari qog'oz ishlab chiqarish, ko'nehilik mahsulotlari, charm mollari ishlab chiqarish sohasi, kumush va qo'rg'oshin konlari, zarbxonalar ham faoliyat ko'rsatgan.

Hunarmandchilik sohasining taraqqiyoti natijasida boshqa davlatlarga diplomatik vakillar yuborilib, narsa-buyumlar ayriboshlangan. Yurtimizda yetishtirilgan bo'z, kiyim-kechak, qilich, egar-jabduq, idishlar, zargarlik buyumlari, dori-darmon, quruq meva kabi mollar olib borilgan.

Shaharlar kengayib, hunarmandchilik, tijorat, ma'rifat, ilm-fan hamda madaniyatning markaziga aylandi. Hunarmandchilikning turli tarmoqlari rivoj topib, qo'li gul mohir hunarmandlarning nozik did va ijodiy mahorati bilan yasagan buyum-u asboblari hamda zeb-ziynatlari o'ziga xos yuksak san'at asari darajasiga yetgan. Sug'orma dehqonchilik, chorvachilik va hunarmandchilikning taraqqiyoti o'z navbatida ichki va tashqi tijoratning kengayishiga, tashqi bozor bilan olib borilgan aloqalarning mustahkamlanishiga olib kelgan. Mashaqqatli mehnat, dehqonchilikning barokati, rohat-u uqubati, yerga egalik qilish munosabatlari xalqimizning turmush tarziga kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatib, insonlarda pok vijdon, sabr-qanoat qilish odobini shakllantirgan. Qadimdan o'zbek milliy hunarmandchiligi sayqallanib, yanada rivoj topib kelmoqda. Xonlik, amirlik davrida ham hunarmandlarning alohida mahallalari bo'lgan.

Kulolchilik, dehqonchilikdan tortib bo'yoqchilik-bo'zchilikka ham mavjud bo'lgan kasblar hozir avlodlar tomonidan foydalanib kelinmoqda.

Temirchi – temirni bolg'alab, undan turli buyumlar yasaydigan usta.

Temirchilik – 1. Kasb oti. Temirchilik bilan ro'zg'or tebratmoq. 2. Temirchilarning do'kon yoki ishxonalari o'rnatilgan rasta.

Tegirmonchi – tegirmon egasi, xo'jayini yoki tegirmonda ishlaydigan kishi².

Yuqorida nomlari tilga olingan kasblar bilan bog'liq quyidagi maqollar mavjud:

1. Temirchi boltaga yolchimas,

To'quvchi – xaltaga.

2. Etikdo'zning etigi yirtiq,

¹O'zbekiston tarixi: 7- sinf uchun darslik. Qayta ishlangan ikkinchi nashr / Muallif A.Muhammadjonov. – Toshkent. "Sharq", 2013. – 160 b.

² O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. Ikki jildlik. 2-jild. A-R. Moskva: Rus tili. 1981, 717 b.

Temirchining teshasi kemtik.

3. **Yakanchining** ming urgani – temirchining bir urgani.
4. Zargarning ming urgani – **chilangarning** bir urgani.
5. Ignachining ming urgani – temirchining bir urgani.
6. Temirchining qo`lida temir erib suv bo`lar.
7. **So`zangarning** ming urgani – chilangarning bir urgani.
8. Temirchidan temir so`rama.
9. Tegirmonchi deb ko`sani uyg`otma.
10. Usta to`shakka yolchimas,
Temirchi to`qaga yolchimas.
11. Temirchining bir urgani – **bosqonchining** ming urgani.
12. Uchqundan qo`rqqan temirchi bo`lmas.
13. **Yo`lchi** yo`lini bilar, tegirmonchi do`lini.
14. Misgarning ming urgani – bosqonchining bir urgani.
15. Ko`mirni o`g`irlagan temirchi,
Baloga qolgan ko`mirchi.
16. Temirchining bir urgani.
Ko`mirchining ming urgani.
17. Omadning shishasi temirchining **dandonini** sindirar.
18. Temirchi taqaga yolchimas,
Bo`zchi – belboqqa.
19. Temirchiga ko`mirchi hokim.
20. Temirchidan ko`mir so`rama.
21. **Ninachining** ming urgani
Temirchining bir urgani.
22. Podachiga yordamchi,
Temirchiga - bosqonchi.
23. Temirchining ming urgani,
Bosqonchining bir urgani.
24. Temirchi to`qaga yolchimas.

Temirchilik kishilik jamiyatining eng qadimgi davrlarida paydo bo`lgan. Mil.avv. 3-4 ming yillik Eron, Mesopotamiya, Misrda temirni sovuqlayin va qizdirib bolg`alab, turli xil aslahalar, mehnat qurollari va boshqa buyumlar yasalgani ma'lum. O`zbekiston hududida temirchilik ishi maxsus do`konda amalga oshirilgan. Temirchi temirni otashxonadagi o`tga qo`yib qizdiradi, metall tobiga kelib, oq tusga kirgach, uni sandonga qo`yib zarur shaklga kirguncha bolg`alaydi.

Bu ishlar usta, bozg`onchi va damgir tomonidan bajarilgan. Temirchilik hozir ham keng ko`lamda saqlanib qolgan.³ Temirchilik do`konida - o`choq, qo`ra, supa, o`ra, cho`pkunda, ish qurollaridan: sandon, bosqon, bolg`a, ombur, egov, charx, dam va hokazolar bo`lgan.

Uchqundan qo`rqqan temirchi bo`lmas. Temirchilik o`ziga yarasha mashaqqatli kasb hisoblanadi. Temirchining kundalik mehnati, albatta, otashxona bilan bog`liq bo`ladi. Shu sababli

³ O`zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi.

ushbu kasbni tanlashdan oldin mashaqqatlarini hisobga olgan holda qolgan barcha vazifalarni zimmaga olish kerak.

Temirchidan ko`mir so`rama. Temirchilik kasbining asosiy ozuqasi ko`mir hisoblanadi. Cho`g`da erigan temirni temirchilar istagan shaklga solib mehnat qurollari yasashadi. Hozirda zamonaviy texnika va texnologiya taraqqiy etgan sharoitda turli xil asbob-uskunalar ishlab chiqilgan. Ammo qadimda esa asosiy ish faqatgina ko`mir orqali bo`lgan. Ko`mir bo`lmasa ish to`xtab qolgan.

Yo`lchi yo`lini bilar, tegirmonchi do`lini. Do`l – tegirmon toshi tepasiga o`rnatilgan piramida shaklidagi idish xampa (tortiladigan don do`lga solinib, undan kosa orqali toshga tushadi)⁴. Har bir ishni uning mohir ustasigina biladi. Yo`lchi ketayotgan manzilini, qaysi yo`l qisqa va xavfsiz ekanligini biladi. Tegirmonchi esa kasbining sir-asrorini chetdagi insonlardan mukammalroq biladi. Har kim o`z ishining ustasi hisoblanadi.

Ignachining ming urgani – temirchining bir urgani. Temirchilik og`ir va mashaqqatli kasb hisoblanadi. Og`ir sharoitda bo`lganligi sababli umri olov jizillab turgan o`choq yonida kechadi. Ignachi va temirchi kasbini taqqoslaganda yoki oddiy bir nina va temirdan tayyorlangan biror ish qurolini taqqoslaganda ikkala kasb o`rtasidagi tafovut bilinadi. Ignachi nozik harakatlar bilan mehnat qurolini yasaydi, temirchi esa zahmat bilan. Ignachining mingta harakat qilgani temirchining bir harakati bilan tengdir.

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